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Potential Drug-Drug Interactions in Hospitalized Patients

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Drug-drug interactions (DDIs) are receiving increased attention due to their potential to cause unexpected effects, especially in patients using multiple medications. Polypharmacy is a significant risk factor, particularly for the elderly and those with comorbidities. Evaluating prescriptions carefully can help reduce these issues. This survey focused on assessing the prevalence and severity of DDIs in hospitalized patients with cardiovascular disease.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective survey was conducted on 180 hospitalized hypertensive patient files of the cardiovascular and diabetes unit in Elbasan regional hospital from 2021 to 2023. Potential DDIs were identified using Medscape Drug Interaction Checker. The data were analyzed using SPSS₂₁ software.

Results: Among 180 patients, 83% were exposed to at least one DDI. Out of the 972 potential interactions identified, 50.80% were pharmacokinetic type, 38.14% were pharmacodynamic, and 3.06% were unknown mechanisms. Serious potential DDIs accounted for 13.50% of the interactions; 65.61% were moderate interactions; and 20.89% were minor interactions. Number of drugs used by patients/day was oscillated from 2 to 16. Occurrence was significantly more prevalent in patients with a higher number of drugs, co-morbidity, and longer lengths of stay in the hospital.

Conclusion: According to this survey, it can be concluded that there was a high prevalence of potential DDIs in the regional hospital when the survey was conducted, and some factors that can influence were the increased number of drugs per patient, comorbidities, and length of hospital stay which were to be associated with the occurrence of potential DDIs.

Keywords: *Drug-drug interaction, Hospitalized patients, Polypharmacy, Pharmacokinetic interactions, Pharmacodynamic interactions*

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Introduction

Drug therapy is growing more complex, thus making appropriate decisions on drug therapy increasingly challenging. Drug interactions are most important in this context and proper handling of drug-drug interactions (DDIs) may prevent harmful events [1]. DDIs are defined thus: “two or more drugs interacting in such a manner that the effectiveness or toxicity of one or more drugs is altered [2], [3], [4]. DDI in patients receiving multidrug therapy is a major concern. Such interactions may lead to an increased risk of hospitalization and higher healthcare costs [5].

The prevalence of DDIs is higher in developing countries where polypharmacy is common due to a lack of strict regulation and monitoring techniques. DDIs represent an important and widely under-recognized source of medication errors. Despite evidence of harmful outcomes related to many DDIs, factors associated with such events have not been fully elucidated, and little is known about the characteristics of the patients exposed to DDIs [6]. DDIs in patients receiving multi-drug therapies are of wide concern [7]. In particular, cardiac patients are vulnerable to DDIs due to their advanced age, polypharmacy, and the influence of heart diseases on drug metabolism [8].

Polypharmacy and adverse drug events continue to be difficult problems in modern healthcare despite continuing efforts to reduce their occurrence. Increased incidence of adverse drug events has been associated with a variety of healthcare environments, including the intensive care unit and various emergency settings. Patients treated with complex medical regimens in various combinations carry the potential for multiple DDI and ADRs. The frequent multiple co-morbidities in this patient population, including renal and liver dysfunction, poor nutritional status, and altered protein binding, amplify the risk of clinically significant drug interactions [9].

The ability to recognize, optimize patient outcomes, and manage DDIs is a crucial role of pharmacists [10]. It is imperative for pharmacists to identify those DDIs and notify the clinicians so that appropriate safety measures and monitoring methods can be implemented [11]. The prescribers or physicians and their patients need to be aware of drug-induced hazards, preventive measures, and management approaches [12].

Pharmacists, being clinical experts should be involved in conducting the clinical trials which will illustrate their role in the health care system. In this way, pharmacists can make their way into disease management. Although pharmacists are part of Hospital settings in developing countries they have no practical role, as the prescriptions are not forwarded to the pharmacists for review and the patients are dependent on physicians.

Wrong practices and an increased trend of polypharmacy have not only affected public health but also put a financial burden on financially compromised patients [13].

This survey aimed to assess potential DDI's prevalence, severity, and significance in hospitalized patients with cardiovascular diseases.

Material and Methods

A randomized retrospective cross-sectional survey was conducted at regional Elbasan hospital in the cardiovascular and diabetes unit, by analyzing 180 files of patients hospitalized with the diagnosis of hypertension. The database was prepared to collect demographic data on patients, such as gender and age, hospital admission and discharge dates, hospitalization diagnoses, concomitant diseases, drugs used for medication, undesirable reactions of medicines that may have arisen, and interactions of drugs derived from Medscape Drug Interaction Checker online. The statistical processing of the results obtained is done with Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21.

The survey proposal was approved by the Ethical Committee of ALDENT University.

Results and Discussion

A total of 180 hospitalized hypertensive patients' medical records were analyzed retrospectively in this survey. The average number of drugs per patient was 6.2067 ± 2.36 , whereas the oscillation of the number of medications used by patients was 2 – 16/day. Many combinations of active substances were present in the prescription for medical treatment of cardiovascular diseases.

The female and male ratio was 42.77%:57.23% which is in line with the fact that men are more prone to heart disease compared to women [14]. The average age of the patients was 65.37 ± 11.82 years, and it oscillated from 32 to 93 years. The mean age was similar to that reported in other published studies [15], [16]. 61.66% of the patients included in this survey were in the age group of 61 up to more than 80 years. The mean number of drugs the patients took was 6.2067, which is similar to one published study [17].

Table 1. General patients' characteristics.

Variable	Frequency %
Gender	
Female	77 (42.77%)
Male	103 (57.23%)
Age (mean \pm SD)	
30 - 40	5 (2.78%)
41 - 50	10 (5.56%)
51 - 60	54 (30.00%)
61 - 70	50 (27.78%)
71 - 80	45 (25.00%)
➤ 80	16 (8.88%)
Drugs (mean \pm SD)	
2	2 (1.09%)
3 - 4	43 (23.59%)
5 - 6	67 (36.61%)
7 - 8	42 (22.95%)
➤ 8	29 (15.85%)

It is worth noting that in scientific literature there is no exact definition of the term polypharmacy depending on the number of drugs the patient uses, so some authors define it as the use of two or more drugs [18], [19], [20], [21], four or more drug [22], five or more drugs [21], [23], [24], [25] five or more drugs at the same time [25], and six or more medication per day [26]. For the interpretation of the results of this survey on the term polypharmacy, we based on the proposal of Suchopar and Prokes [26]. Most patients (57.22 %, n=103) included in our survey met polypharmacy criteria.

Figure 1. Correlation between number of medicines/day and number of interaction.

Figure 2. Types of drug-drug interactions

Figure 3. Severity of drug-drug interaction

Figure 4. Co-morbidity status of patients

In cases where many drugs are prescribed together, they may interfere with each other and cause potential drug interactions. Though, drug-drug interactions are widespread among cardiac patients. Rates of all potential DDIs ranging from 9.2% to 78.8% have been described in published studies [16], [27]. This broad range of prevalence values may be partially explained by factors such as study design, methodology, definitions, characteristics of the population, number of medications prescribed, therapeutic traditions, and compendium of drug interactions [27], [28] as well as the variation to the difference in the level of hospitals, availability of qualified health professional, the sample size used in the study areas and the available rules and regulations by the pharmacy unit in monitoring and prevention of potential DDIs. Proper management of DDIs should be supported by suitable measures like therapeutic drug monitoring and dose adjustment techniques to reduce the likelihood of an adverse outcome.

Data obtained from our survey have shown that 38.80% of prescriptions have more than 6 drugs. The increasing risk of potential drug-drug interactions with increasing age and polypharmacy is well documented [29], [30], [31]. The results obtained by this survey are in line with other studies which also showed that potential DDIs are more frequent in older patients who are on polypharmacy [32], [33], [34]. The results of this survey confirm that most interactions have arisen in older patients who used more than six drugs, and in older patients with concomitant diseases, such as diabetes mellitus, myocardial infarction, and heart attacks. (Figure 1). Correlation between the number of drugs and the number of interactions, by using Spearman's test, has shown a coefficient

$r = 0.616$; $nr. 180$, and $P < 0.001$.

The patterns of incidence of DDIs of the present survey showed that they are positively associated with patient's age, gender, number of drugs prescribed, and length of hospital stay which according to this survey was 4.7278 ± 3.6522 days, ranging from 1 to 24 days.

The prevalence rate for all potential DDIs in this survey was 47.22%. A total of 972 potential DDIs were identified, which corresponds to 5.40 DDIs per patient. The prevalence of DDIs 47.22% derived from this survey was less than that found by Kothari and Ganguly [35] (71%) and is in line with the prevalence found by Bjorkman et al. [33] (41.50%). It may be attributed to the fact that cardiovascular drugs are the most common drugs to cause DDIs [36], [37].

Data from the present survey regarding the types of drug interactions have shown that, out of 972 DDIs, 58.80% were pharmacokinetic interactions, 38.14% were pharmacodynamic and 3.06% were with unknown mechanisms.

Concerning the severity of interactions, the survey revealed that most interactions were moderate 65.61%, serious 13.50%, and mild 20.89%. On the assessment of the severity of DDIs, the majority of the cases were classified as moderate in severity (>65.61%), which is in line with the Indian study [8].

Conclusion

According to this survey, it can be concluded that there was a high prevalence of potential DDIs in the regional hospital when the survey was conducted, and some factors that can influence were the increased number of drugs per patient, co-morbidities, and length of hospital stay which were to be associated with the occurrence of potential DDIs.

Acknowledgment

Not applicable.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests.

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